

Frederic Chopin:

The Voice and Music of Polish Romanticism

Daniel Szelogowski

MUSC 246-01

Professor Erin Bauer

April 9, 2019

Frederic Chopin (1810–1849) remains one of the most influential composers of the Romantic era, renowned for his virtuoso piano compositions and their unparalleled emotional depth. Deeply rooted in Polish musical traditions, Chopin elevated genres like the mazurka and polonaise to global recognition, blending national identity with innovative harmonic and rhythmic techniques. His works, characterized by lyrical expressiveness and structural originality, reflect both his personal struggles and the political turmoil of his homeland. Despite his frail health and turbulent relationship with George Sand, Chopin achieved remarkable artistic output and groundbreaking contributions to piano music that influenced future Romantic and Impressionist composers. His legacy endures in his timeless compositions, which continue to define Romantic piano music and celebrate the cultural spirit of Poland.

Early Life

Fryderyk Franciszek Chopin's early life, born on March 1st, 1810, began in Żelazowa Wola, Poland. His father Mikołaj (Nicholas), a French émigré in Poland, tutored aristocratic families before becoming a French teacher at the Warsaw lyceum, which Chopin had attended from 1823 to 1826.¹ Both his mother Justyna and eldest sister Ludwika were pianists – of which he had attempted to imitate and create his own music at the piano by age six; not long after taking piano lessons with the virtuoso pianist Wojciech Zywny the following year. Zywny's simple instruction in piano playing was soon left behind by his pupil, who discovered an original approach to the piano and was allowed to develop unhindered by academic rules and formal discipline.²

After starting piano lessons as a child, it was not long after he began receiving invitations to play at private soirees, and he made his first public appearance at a charity concert at eight years old. By age eleven, he had performed in front of the Russian tsar Alexander I.³ Within this same period, he was already writing a multitude of piano pieces before enrolling in the Warsaw

Conservatory of Music by age 16, under the direction of Chopin's music theory tutor, composer Joseph Elsner.⁴ By this time, he had written for the Russian military band to play on parade, soon after following with polonaises, variations, mazurkas, waltzes, and a rondo. Britannica discusses the influence left by his new tutor:

No better teacher could have been found, for, while insisting on a traditional training, Elsner, as a Romantically inclined composer himself, realized that Chopin's individual imagination must never be checked by purely academic demands. Even before he came under Elsner's eye, Chopin had shown interest in the folk music of the Polish countryside and had received those impressions that later gave an unmistakable national coloring to his work. At the conservatory [Chopin] was put through a solid course of instruction in harmony and composition; in piano playing he was allowed to develop a high degree of individuality.⁵

Striving to push Chopin to a vaster musical experience and broaden his knowledge, his parents saved money to send him to Vienna. After touring Berlin in 1828, Chopin visited Vienna and made his performance debut there in 1829, confirming his success as a performer by his second concert.⁶ During his return home, Chopin prepared himself for further achievements abroad by writing his Piano Concerto No. 1 in E Minor and his Piano Concerto No. 2 in F Minor, as well as other works for piano and orchestra designed to exploit his brilliantly original piano style.⁷ By this same time, he also began composing his first etudes in order to gain mastery of his new style. Chopin gained traction soon after: his name became known outside of Poland after his Variations, Op. 2, for piano and orchestra on Mozart's "La ci darem la mano," written when he was 17, were published in 1830 – prompting Robert Schumann's famous accolade in the *Allgemeine musikalische Zeitung*: "Hats off, gentlemen! A genius!"⁸ After performing his pair of piano concertos in Warsaw during the spring and autumn of that year, he left Poland to visit Italy and Germany to continue his studies. Shortly after reaching Vienna, he received news of the Polish revolt against Russian rule, causing him to remain in Vienna profitless for eight months before heading for Paris, where he would remain and never return to his home country.⁹

Later Life

Arriving in Paris, Chopin quickly connected with the Parisian artistic views and schools of thought – the center of “Romanticism.” After making his debut at the Salle Pleyel in February 1832 – including Franz Liszt, Luigi Cherubini, and Felix Mendelssohn in the audience – he became one of the French capital’s celebrities.¹⁰ Not long after, Chopin established ties with those composers of his audience, among Hector Berlioz and Vincenzo Bellini, as well as artist Eugene Delacroix, who painted an oil canvas portrait of him in 1838. Chopin initially attempted to give solo concerts, but they turned out to be financial failures due to the extreme intimacy and delicacy of his piano works being performed in large concert halls. To support himself and to earn his living, Chopin engaged in private piano tutoring and playing small piano pieces in salons of the French aristocracy, the result of an introduction to the wealthy Rothschild family.¹¹ Following brief uncertainty, Chopin settled down to his new primary life business of composing and teaching; after overcoming his life of poverty in Vienna, he was now set with high income and no longer worried about the performance life, which he disliked – finally displaying his more conservative, “normal” self not often portrayed by other narrative.¹²

During this time of work, he seldom performed, primarily at salons and in his apartment. In 1835, he visited his parents in Carlsbad, Czech Republic, where he would see them for the last time, among the Wodzinskis, old friends from Warsaw.¹³ The following year, Chopin traveled to Dresden and Marienbad to visit the Wodzinski family, of which he had proposed to Maria, which her mother had approved; however, his sister Ludwika had inscribed seven pieces of his music in an album to which had been sent to his fiancé while he had continued traveling to Leipzig at the end of the year – the letter she had sent in return “thanking” him would be the last word he received from her.¹⁴ Around this same time, he had also lived near Franz Liszt in Paris, where they

performed together several times between 1833, beginning with a benefit concert organized by Berlioz for his wife, to 1841, at a charity concert for the Beethoven Memorial in Bonn that was held at the Paris Conservatory and Salle Pleyel.¹⁵ Although greatly respectful to each other and shared admiration, the two had a love-hate relationship – Chopin especially showed jealousy regarding Liszt’s piano virtuosity. His Op. 10 Etudes were dedicated to Liszt, and his performance of them left Chopin’s jealousy expressed in writing to fellow musician Ferdinand Hiller, stating, “I should like to rob him of the way he plays my studies.”¹⁶ Among this, Liszt performed a nocturne of his in 1843, to which Chopin had forced an apology for his overly intricate and embellished playing style of the piece, stating that he should play the piece as written or not at all.¹⁷ After this event, the two composers had become mostly separated, though Chopin still referred to Liszt as his friend in letters even five years afterward – although there was tension between them as a result of Liszt’s mistress’ obsession with Chopin, and Liszt’s increasing relationship with George Sand.¹⁸

In 1836, he met novelist Aurore Dudevant, better known by her pseudonym George Sand, with whom he had begun a relationship in 1838 during the summer. The two had lived in a villa rented on the island of Majorca with Sand’s two children. However, they had been forced to leave after the owner had been rumored to have tuberculosis – the two were left to live in a monastery in Valldemosa, the nearby remote village.¹⁹ The living conditions were unpleasant, and lacked a decent piano, which hastened Chopin’s decline in health and hindered his artistic production as he grew weaker.²⁰ Although seriously ill, he completed his Op. 28 of 24 preludes.²¹ In haste, Sand pushed to depart immediately, to which they would arrive in Marseille, France, in March of 1839, where a physician was able to allow Chopin to recover sufficiently within three months; by the summer, they moved into Sand’s country house in Hohant, where Chopin would experience the most productive and happiest period of his life among returning to his business of privately

teaching piano.²² As well, his new works grew in demand heavily, allowing him a better choice of publishers and a much higher income – though still coping with recurring bouts of illness and emotional swings. Libbey notes that this was also a time of astounding production for compositions:

During the 1840s, [Chopin] produced a remarkable body of compositions that included the Ballades in A-flat, Op. 47, and F minor, Op. 52, the Mazurkas of Opp. 50, 56, 59, 63 and 67, the A-flat major Polonaise, Op. 53, the Nocturnes of Opp. 48, 55 and 62, and the Sonata in B minor, Op. 58 (1844). The best of these works — the B minor Sonata, the Op. 55 Nocturnes and the Op. 56 Mazurkas — are characterized by remarkable refinement and complexity, along with a newly rich sense of ambivalence. The opening movement of the sonata finds Chopin at the summit of inspiration, weaving turbulence and romantic yearning into a beautifully seamless expression.²³

Chopin found this time to indulge in peace and search for musical perfection – anxious to further develop his musical ideas to be larger and more complex. He had also been in contact with musicologists in Paris and requested treatises from them to strengthen his ability in counterpoint, among also growing his harmonic vocabulary; particularly valuing sensuous beauty rather than an underlying “program” or descriptive titles, which he had been disgusted by.²⁴ The only piece he actually entitled was the Funeral March; the rest were given by others through interpretation, some including George Sand.²⁵

End of Life, Beyond Death

Chopin’s relationship with Sand grew especially tense as a result of Sand’s daughter, Solange’s engagement in 1843 to sculptor Auguste Clesinger – the result of which caused a massive feud between her and Sand, to which Chopin took Solange’s side.²⁶ This “betrayal” as recounted by Sand in her uncontrolled jealousy of her now rival-daughter shook the relationship between her and Chopin. Although he had been indifferent to her political hounding, she looked down upon his own friends.²⁷ Jachimecki notes the paradigm shift in the two’s relationship:

As [Chopin’s] illness progressed, Sand had become less of a lover and more of a nurse to Chopin, whom she called her “third child”. In letters to third parties, she vented her

impatience, referring to him as a “child,” a “little angel”, a “sufferer” and a “beloved little corpse.” In 1847 Sand published her novel *Lucrezia Floriani*, whose main characters – a rich actress and a prince in weak health – could be interpreted as Sand and Chopin; the story was uncomplimentary to Chopin, who could not have missed the allusions as he helped [her] correct the printer’s galleys.²⁸

By 1847, the two had been separated, unfixable as a result of pride preventing the reconciliation both had desired, and Chopin had given up hope on his struggle with illness and fell gravely ill.²⁹ The revolution in Paris in February 1848 left him depressed and spiritually broken, and the following April, he accepted an invitation for an invitation to stay in England and Scotland; he had been well received in London, though he struggled through giving lessons and appearing at parties.³⁰ His illness left him unable to socialize and compose, and he wrote virtually nothing from then on. Chopin’s last public performance was a benefit concert for Polish refugees in November of 1848 at the Guildhall in London, returning to Paris shortly after, where he would remain exhaustedly until his death in October the following year – his body was buried at the cemetery of Pere Lachaise. His heart was entombed separately at the Church of the Holy Cross in Warsaw.³¹ On his deathbed, a handful of his closest friends and his sister Ludwika remained with him and played music at his request; after his death the morning of October 17th, 1849, Solange’s now husband Clesinger made a cast of his left hand and his death mask.³²

At Chopin’s funeral, which was held at the Church of the Madeleine in Paris and had been delayed nearly two weeks until October 30th, over three thousand people from distances as far as Vienna, Berlin, and London arrived without invitations and were denied entrance as tickets were required due to the number of attendees expected.³³ Among the music performed included Mozart’s Requiem and Chopin’s own Preludes No. 4 and No. 6. Prince Adam Czartoryski led the procession to Pere Lachaise Cemetery, where Chopin’s Funeral March from his Piano Sonata No. 2 was played by his graveside.³⁴ The cause of his death has led to a multitude of possibilities being explored; Ironpower discusses the development of such a phenomenon:

His death certificate gave the cause of death as tuberculosis, and his physician, Cruveilhier, was then the leading French authority on this disease. Other possibilities that have been advanced have included cystic fibrosis, cirrhosis, and alpha 1-antitrypsin deficiency. A visual examination of Chopin's preserved heart, conducted in 2014 and published in 2017, suggested that the likely cause of his death was a rare case of pericarditis caused by complications of chronic tuberculosis.³⁵

Compositions

Chopin left over 230 surviving compositions for a multitude of instrumentations. He was influenced significantly by classical era musicians: Clementi and Hummel's techniques, which he used with his students, and the writing styles of Beethoven, Haydn, Mozart, and Clementi.³⁶ The compositions of his early life were particularly influenced by Friedrich Kalkbrenner and Ignaz Moscheles, but stated that Bach and Mozart were the two most important composers who shaped his musical interpretation.³⁷ He was fascinated by Bach, and as a result, left his music as not the "wild and frenzied romantic" style that some may believe; rather than the musical attitude and imagination of Liszt or Wagner, Chopin's music is simple and is meant to reflect his love for simplicity.

Chopin noted that "after mastering all sorts of difficulties [it] is simplicity with all its charm that stands out as the final sanction of art."³⁸ Resulting from this also is the highly prominent influence of Italian opera and Polish folk music, which shaped his style of ornamentation of opera and melodic lines similar to Polish music in his modal and drone usages. Most solo works of his follow this same suit: the polonaise, mazurka, waltz, nocturne, and waltz styles were all based on cultural ideas and explored on deeper levels, scherzi, etudes, impromptus, ballades, and preludes were written as free-standing concert pieces, among further exploring more standard forms as the rondo and sonata as well.³⁹ Chopin notably sought to publicize the Polish dance – the mazurka – which was a success, among setting the standard for the polonaise as a musical form; and through his solo voice works, he created the first true instance of Polish art song.⁴⁰ Among his

other sets of instrumentations include piano/orchestra and piano/strings. Britannica describes the composer's heavy influence of his home country on his music:

[Chopin] found within himself and in the tragic story of Poland the chief sources of his inspiration. The theme of Poland's glories and sufferings was constantly before him, and he transmuted the primitive rhythms and melodies of his youth into enduring art forms. At the same time, he subtly differentiated [the] intimate poetic inspiration of the mazurka from the more outward-looking, ceremonial aspect of the polonaise, which [he] expanded to the proportions of symphonic poems for the piano.⁴¹

In terms of harmonic innovations, which were largely the result of his improvisational technique, Chopin, especially in his ballades, uses asymmetrical strophic lengths and "implied" cross-rhythms to manipulate the musical texture, as well as the heavy use of discretionary rubato – disturbing the tempo. Among this complex analysis is his grandeur of pedal points and tones, which contest the current use of legato and slurred motives.⁴² Additionally, Chopin developed his own musical ideas, including the use of cadences delayed by chords outside the home key, suddenly shifting to a remote key, and chord progressions that anticipate shifting tonality through modal harmony seen in later composers such as Claude Debussy.⁴³ His melodic style was highly personal, expressive, and heartfelt – romantic in style, but with simplicity and purity that develops a poetic idea; at the center of this development process is a basis of improvisation, especially reminiscent of the works of Schubert.⁴⁴

Influence

Frederic Chopin was by all means a man of his country; his music defined that of his country, and his country defined his music. Particularly important is the more sympathetic treatment of his relationship with George Sand: a pair that showed its incompatibility and seeks to reflect on Chopin not as a hopeless romantic but as a strong musician who went through life struggles yet embodied simplicity and reservation in his music. His unique, personalized style was expressive of himself and the people of his home – his music recreates the feelings of anger,

rebellion, frustration, and hope felt by the Polish residents suffering under the times of war the country lived under during its partition between Russia, Austria, and Prussia. Among this, his first composition was a polonaise, and his last was a mazurka. These compositions were all ahead of their time in articulate, dynamic, harmonic, and melodic styles and defined the views of the Polish through his music. Chopin left a lasting influence on both the country and future composers to this day – he inspired the creation of new genres, techniques, and styles that set the footing for new and upcoming musicians, and in his home country were left the creation of the International Chopin Piano Competition, initiated in 1927. The renaming of his past conservatory, the Warsaw Institute of Music, to the Fryderyk Chopin University of Music in 2008.⁴⁵ It is no surprise that a composer of his genius left such a profound impact – especially on his homeland – one that continues to inspire musicians and resonate with audiences worldwide.

Notes

1. “Frédéric Chopin” Britannica Online Academic Edition, 2019, Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.
2. Green, Janet. “Chopin, Frederic Francois.” *Musical Biographies*. Owen Press, 2008: 136–144.
3. Ibid.
4. Chissell, Joan. *Chopin. The Great Composers*. New York: T.Y. Crowell, 1965.
5. “Frédéric Chopin” Britannica Online Academic Edition, 2019, Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.
6. Ibid.
7. Ibid.
8. Libbey, Ted. “The Life And Music Of Frederic Chopin.” NPR. March 02, 2010. Accessed April 23, 2019. <https://www.npr.org/2011/07/18/123967818/the-life-and-music-of-frederic-chopin>
9. Ibid.
10. Marek, George R., and Gordon-Smith, Maria. *Chopin*. First ed. New York: Harper & Row, 1978.
11. Green, Janet. “Chopin, Frederic Francois.” *Musical Biographies*. Owen Press, 2008: 136–144.
12. Marek, George R., and Gordon-Smith, Maria. *Chopin*. First ed. New York: Harper & Row, 1978.
13. Hedley, Arthur. *Selected Correspondence Of Fryderyk Chopin*. Andesite Press, 2015.
14. Ibid.
15. *Great Big Book of Classical Sheet Music: Complete Chopin*. Vol. 1. Ironpower Publishing, 2018.
16. Ibid.
17. Hedley, Arthur. *Selected Correspondence Of Fryderyk Chopin*. Andesite Press, 2015.
18. Ibid.
19. “Frédéric Chopin” Britannica Online Academic Edition, 2019, Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.
20. Ibid.
21. Libbey, Ted. “The Life And Music Of Frederic Chopin.” NPR. March 02, 2010. Accessed April 23, 2019. <https://www.npr.org/2011/07/18/123967818/the-life-and-music-of-frederic-chopin>
22. “Frédéric Chopin” Britannica Online Academic Edition, 2019, Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.
23. Libbey, Ted. “The Life And Music Of Frederic Chopin.” NPR. March 02, 2010. Accessed April 23, 2019. <https://www.npr.org/2011/07/18/123967818/the-life-and-music-of-frederic-chopin>
24. “Frédéric Chopin” Britannica Online Academic Edition, 2019, Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.
25. *Great Big Book of Classical Sheet Music: Complete Chopin*. Vol. 1. Ironpower Publishing, 2018.
26. Jensen, Katharine. *The Chopin Affair: George Sand’s Rivalry with her Daughter*, *Nineteenth-Century Contexts*, 2013: 35:1, 41-64.
27. Ibid.
28. Jachimecki, Zdzisław. “Chopin, Fryderyk Franciszek”. *Polski słownik biograficzny*, Kraków: Polska Akademia Umiejętności, 1937: 420–26.
29. “Frédéric Chopin” Britannica Online Academic Edition, 2019, Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.
30. Ibid.

31. Libbey, Ted. "The Life And Music Of Frederic Chopin." NPR. March 02, 2010. Accessed April 23, 2019. <https://www.npr.org/2011/07/18/123967818/the-life-and-music-of-frederic-chopin>
32. *Great Big Book of Classical Sheet Music: Complete Chopin*. Vol. 1. Ironpower Publishing, 2018.
33. Ibid.
34. Atwood, William G. *The Parisian Worlds of Frederic Chopin*. New Haven: Yale University Press, 1999: 409.
35. *Great Big Book of Classical Sheet Music: Complete Chopin*. Vol. 1. Ironpower Publishing, 2018.
36. Ibid.
37. Ibid.
38. Landormy, Paul. "Chopin." *The Musical Quarterly* 15 (1929): 160.
39. Libbey, Ted. "The Life And Music Of Frederic Chopin." NPR. March 02, 2010. Accessed April 23, 2019. <https://www.npr.org/2011/07/18/123967818/the-life-and-music-of-frederic-chopin>
40. Schultz, Benjamin. *Singing in Polish: A Guide to Polish Lyric Diction and Vocal Repertoire*. Lanham, MD: Rowman & Littlefield, 2016.
41. "Frédéric Chopin" Britannica Online Academic Edition, 2019, Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.
42. Barthold, Kenneth. "Chopin." *BBC Music Magazine* 5, no. 2 (1996): 24.
43. *Great Big Book of Classical Sheet Music: Complete Chopin*. Vol. 1. Ironpower Publishing, 2018.
44. Ibid.
45. Ibid.

References

- Atwood, William G. *The Parisian Worlds of Frederic Chopin*. New Haven: Yale University Press, 1999: 409.
- Barthold, Kenneth. "Chopin." *BBC Music Magazine* 5, no. 2 (1996): 24.
- "Frédéric Chopin" *Britannica Online Academic Edition*, 2019, Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.
- Chissell, Joan. *Chopin. The Great Composers*. New York: T.Y. Crowell, 1965.
- Green, Janet. "Chopin, Frederic Francois." *Musical Biographies*. Owen Press, 2008: 136–144.
- Hedley, Arthur. *Selected Correspondence Of Fryderyk Chopin*. Andesite Press, 2015.
- Great Big Book of Classical Sheet Music: Complete Chopin*. Vol. 1. Ironpower Publishing, 2018.
- Jachimecki, Zdzisław. "Chopin, Fryderyk Franciszek". *Polski słownik biograficzny*, Kraków: Polska Akademia Umiejętności, 1937: 420–26.
- Jensen, Katharine. *The Chopin Affair: George Sand's Rivalry with her Daughter, Nineteenth-Century Contexts*, 2013: 35:1, 41-64.
- Landormy, Paul. "Chopin." *The Musical Quarterly* 15 (1929): 160.
- Libbey, Ted. "The Life And Music Of Frederic Chopin." NPR. March 02, 2010. Accessed April 23, 2019. <https://www.npr.org/2011/07/18/123967818/the-life-and-music-of-frederic-chopin>.
- Marek, George R., and Gordon-Smith, Maria. *Chopin*. First ed. New York: Harper & Row, 1978.
- Schultz, Benjamin. *Singing in Polish: A Guide to Polish Lyric Diction and Vocal Repertoire*. Lanham, MD: Rowman & Littlefield, 2016.